

Assessment of Experience and Qualification on Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary School Teachers' in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated Assessment of Experience and Qualification on Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria. The research was guided by two research objectives two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was made up of 481 Hausa language teachers' teaching in public senior secondary schools in Katsina state. The sample of the study consists of 217 Hausa language teachers selected from the target population using proportionate stratified sampling technique. A self-made research questionnaire instrument titled "Teachers Experience and Qualification in the Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum Questionnaire (TEQIHLQCQ)" was used for data collection. Reliability index of the instrument obtained was 0.87. Data collected for the study was subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics, while the two null hypothesis were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed there was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation ($F_{(6/194)} = 125.368$, and $p = .000$), the conclusion of the revealed that teachers experience and qualification has positive significant impact on the use of methodology and the effectiveness in implementing the senior secondary school Hausa Curriculum. It was further Recommended there is need for Zonal Education Quality Assurance staff to ensure proper monitoring and supervision of all schools offering Hausa language so as to have effective implementation of the Hausa language curriculum in Katsina State.

Keyword: Experience, Qualification, Curriculum Implementation

Introduction

Education is the process of acquiring relevant and worthwhile skills, attitudes, values and competencies in order to make one useful to oneself, family, community and the nation at large. According to the National Policy on Education (FRN 2014), education is an instrument par excellence for national development and social change. Using education as an instrument per excellence for the desired national development; the government intends to make Nigeria a "free and a democratic society, a just and egalitarian society, a united, strong and self-reliant nation, a great and dynamic economy and a land full of bright opportunities for all citizens." (FRN, 2014). The success of any organization depends largely on the quality and strength of its staffs. Ayodele (2000), opined that no matter how efficient and effective an administrator is, he hardly achieves success without the support and cooperation of well qualified and dedicated teachers. Quality of teacher is the pivot and the determinant of education. A school without such calibre of teachers may not be able to achieve the stated goals and objectives of the educational system.

Secondary education is pivotal to a meaningful development of youths who are the leaders of tomorrow. As a matter of fact, the learning and nurturing that occur during these years have a profound impact on each student's opportunities for the future; and the quality of each student's education at the secondary school level has much to do with the course and quality of

his/her life as an adult. Besides, secondary schools are also elaborate, complex mini-societies whose internal organizational structures have a direct impact on the lives of the individuals and groups of individuals who inhabit them. In addition to their formal organizational structures, secondary schools are equally inherent cultural entities replete with amazing arrays of artefacts, rituals, and rites of passage all of which impact directly on the manner in which their inhabitants negotiate the terms of their existence within those institutions. Teacher motivation is very central in energizing the teacher to teach and to seek to impart knowledge effectively. Teachers at all levels of the education system should be adequately trained, respected, remunerated, and be able to participate in decisions affecting their professional lives and teaching environments. When teachers are enabled to do their job effectively, their students are enabled to learn effectively. Around the world there are many similarities and differences among teachers in the way they are trained and certified as professionals to teach in schools. In almost all countries teachers are educated in a university or college. Shiundu (2014) notes that teachers without proper academic and professional qualification fail to do justice to the subject. He further adds that an adequate qualification of the teacher instills self confidence in him and serves as an inspiration to the pupils. An experienced teacher has skills, values and positive attitudes to make the learner be curious, aroused and interested in learning.

Shiundu and Omulando (2015) argued that to most teachers, implementation is their legitimate role in curriculum development. Their reference to the teacher and curriculum is that after a consensus is reached as to what will go into the curriculum of the educational system the next important step is to avail this curriculum package to the educational system, a process that is known as curriculum implementation. Various personnel are involved, but perhaps the one whose role is most important in seeing that programmes are successfully implemented is the teacher, who organizes the learning environment for the benefit of the pupils who must experience curriculum. Many occupations recognize employee's years of experience as a relevant factor in human resource policies, including compensate on systems, benefit packages, and promotion decisions. The idea is that experience, gained over time, enhances the knowledge, skills, and productivity of workers. In education, teacher experience is probably the key factor in personnel policies that affect current employees: it is a cornerstone of traditional single-salary schedules; it drives teacher transfer policies that prioritise seniority; and it is commonly considered a major source of inequity across schools and, therefore, a target for redistribution. The underlying assumption is that experience promotes effectiveness. Human resource is necessary at all levels of education, but most needed at the secondary school level. This is because no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers (FGN, 2009). Teachers are instrumental in translating content standards into teachable classroom lessons. The teacher remains a constant factor in the successful implementation of educational programmes.

It is evident that teacher's experience and qualification have direct correlation with the implementation among senior secondary school curriculum; hence, experience has shown that, there exist differences in terms of effective implementation of Hausa language curriculum between trained Hausa Language teachers and non-Hausa Language experts. This could be seen in terms of wider coverage of the contents of curriculum as well as doing justice to the concepts vis-a-vis use of instructional materials, evaluation, methodology, content coverage, objectives of the lesson, during classroom interaction sessions. It is against this background that the researcher becomes interested in finding out the impact of teacher's experience and qualification in implementing Senior Secondary School Hausa Curriculum in Katsina State, to confirm whether the experience and qualification of Hausa teachers influence the level of implementation, and to find out whether a considerable number of Hausa language teachers have requisite qualification to teach Hausa language at senior secondary schools levels, the years of work experience, the number of training/workshops attended, the knowledge of subject matter, the teacher's personalities, their conditions of service, as well as their motivation are extremely important.

Curriculum implementation is an important segment of teaching and learning process. It has to do with the translation of the curriculum into action. This exercise of the curriculum requires personnel, facilities, instructional materials, good administration and teaching methods among other things needed for curriculum implementation. National Commission for Colleges of Education, (2012). Recently the efforts of the governments and towards the implementation of the new Hausa curriculum for the senior secondary schools have yielded little or no dividends due to issues which are inherent in the implementation of the curriculum. These problems include under funding, non-availability of instructional materials, inadequate classrooms, obsolete instructional materials and non-utilization of teaching and learning facilities, lack of qualified and well experience teachers amongst others. This resulted in producing of half-baked Hausa Language students and public noticed and expressed concern on the competency of teachers trained to teach Hausa language in secondary schools. And this in turn will affect not only Hausa language education but will no doubt hamper the educational development in the country. This prompted the researcher to undertake the study. There by taking a critical look at the impact teachers experience and qualification on implementation of the new Hausa languages curriculum in senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

which comprise all zonal quality assurance unit in Katsina. Katsina zone, Dutsin-ma zone, Kankia Zone, Malumfashi zone, Funtua Zone, Mani Zone and Daura Zone, Safana, Baure, Rimi, Musawa, and Faskari Zone respectively.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study were:

1. To find out the impact of experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria.
2. To find out the impact of qualification on implementation of Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the impact of experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of qualification on effective implementation of Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The following hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. H_{01} . There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa Language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.
2. H_{02} There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study was descriptive survey design, for this study was adopted find out the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation and find out the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. Survey design seeks to investigate the current phenomenon under investigation through people responses opinion and attitude in comparism to establish standard. The population of this study included all public senior secondary school Hausa language teachers from the twelve zonal education quality assurance in Katsina State, i.e. Katsina zone, Kankia zone, Dutsin-ma zone, Daura zone, Baure zone, Funtua zone, Mani zone, Malumfashi zone, Safana zone, Musawa zone, Faskari and Rimi Zone. There are 481 qualified Hausa teachers spread across 12 educational zones in the three senatorial zones in Katsina state based on official data collected from Katsina State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education as at October 2024 The sample of this study consists of 217 Hausa teachers in senior secondary schools in Katsina State. The decision to use 217 sample size is based on the Research Advisors table of sample specification. It indicates that for population of 481 at 95 percent confidence level and margin error of 5 percent, 217 sample size is adequate. The proportionate stratified sampling technique was used in determining the number of Hausa teachers to be used from each zone. . A self-made research questionnaire instrument titled "Teachers Experience and Qualification in the Implementation of Hausa Language Curriculum Questionnaire (TEQIHLCCQ)" was used for data collection. The instrument was pilot tested and the reliability index of the instrument was 0.87. Data collected for the study was subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. The information on the demographic data was analyzed using frequency count and percentage. The research question were answered, the null hypothesis were tested using Analysis of Variance.

Presentation of Result

Research Question 1

What is the impact of experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary school teachers in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Opinion of the Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Experience on Methodology of Hausa Language Curriculum Implementation among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	Responses					N	Mean	STD
		SD	D	U	A	SA			
1	I employ questioning techniques as a means of involving students and helping them find solutions to issues which bear in the learning of Hausa studies.	30	46	48	49	28	201	3.00	1.28
2	I employ all the following methods of instruction during Hausa studies, Group discussion, Storytelling, role play, Drama, Demonstration method, simulation games, problem solving.	27	33	55	39	47	201	3.23	1.34
3	I engage students in group activities such as dialogue, discussion, conversation, in pairs and debate to enhance their communicative competence and proficiency in written and spoken Hausa studies.	36	53	18	52	42	201	3.05	1.44
4	I engage students in field trips and excursion so as to widen their conceptual horizon in the study of Hausa language.	15	64	41	45	36	201	3.11	1.25
5	I engage students in composition writing to develop their writing skills during Hausa studies lessons.	17	68	62	25	29	201	2.91	1.17

The above response in the table 1 above indicated the opinion of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. From the table, it reveals that 4 of the 5 items in this section of the questionnaire received positive responses from the respondents, as the mean scores were 3.00 and above. On the other hand, Item 10 received negative responses from the respondents, as the mean score was below 3.00. Therefore, this implies that the opinion of majority of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was positive, and hence, this is the answer to this research question.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁. There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa Language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, One-way analysis of variance statistic was used. The data was analysed using SPSS v.23.0, and the result was presented in the Tables 2 and 3:

Table 2 Differences in the Opinion of Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Experience on Methodology of Hausa Language Curriculum Implementation among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	1393.177	6	232.196	125.368	.000
Within Groups	359.311	194	1.852		

Total	1752.488	200
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From Table 2: above, the differences in the opinion of respondents on the impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa Language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was $F_{(6/194)} = 125.368$, and $p = .000$. Since the p-value (.000) was less than the alpha value (.05), the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis was adopted. So, the researcher concluded that there was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria?

Table 4: Opinion of the Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Qualification on their Effectiveness in Implementing the Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	Responses					N	Mean	STD
		SD	D	U	A	SA			
7	A good qualified teacher should be able to carry along all category of different learning abilities.	25	39	52	57	28	201	3.12	1.24
8	Teaching of Hausa language requires qualification and special training in NCE, B.A. Ed, M.Ed.	18	66	42	50	25	201	2.99	1.20
9	Students get poor performance because they do not understand the lesson taught by untrained teacher.	49	60	40	34	18	201	2.56	1.27
10	A qualified teacher should focus on comprehension of new concept in the subject content and not on final result.	30	34	50	28	59	201	3.26	1.42
11	Teachers with high level of qualification can help them to motivate students to learn even when they are not willing to learn.	33	44	41	40	43	201	3.08	1.39

Table 4. Indicated the opinion of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. From the table, it reveals that 3 of the 5 items in this section of the questionnaire received positive responses from the respondents, as the mean scores were 3.00 and above. On the other hand, Items 22, and 23 received negative responses from the respondents, as the mean scores were below 3.00. Therefore, this implies that the opinion of majority of the respondents regarding the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was positive, and hence, this is the answer to this research question.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference among respondents on the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, One-way analysis of variance statistic was used. The data was analysed using SPSS v.23.0, and the result was presented in the Tables 5 and 6:

Table 6: Differences in the Opinion of Respondents Regarding the Impact of Teachers' Qualification on their Effectiveness in Implementing the Hausa Language Curriculum among Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	403.929	3	134.643	17.516	.000
Within Groups	1514.290	197	7.687		
Total	1918.219	201			

From Table 6; above, the differences in the opinion of respondents on the impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria was $F_{(3/197)} = 17.516$, and $p = .000$. Since the p-value (.000) was less than the alpha value (.05), the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis was adopted. So, the researcher concluded that there was a significant impact of teachers' qualification and their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

1. There was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria ($F_{(6/194)} = 125.368$, and $p = .000$), and the difference was between almost all groups of respondents except those between 16 to 20 years and 21 to 25 years, and those between 26 to 30 years and 31 to 35 years.
2. There was a significant impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria ($F_{(3/197)} = 17.516$, and $p = .000$), and the difference was between almost all groups of respondents except between those with Degree and those with Masters and PhD qualifications.

Discussion of Findings

One of the major findings of this study is that There was a significant impact of teachers' experience on methodology of Hausa language curriculum implementation among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. This finding agreed with that of Faustina (2014), which implied that teachers' experience have positive impact on selecting and utilising suitable teaching methods for teaching Hausa language. Thus, the higher the teachers' experience a Hausa language teacher possesses the more positive impact he / she will make in ensuring effective use of suitable teaching methods. Therefore, experienced teachers are likely to impact positively towards effective Hausa language curriculum implementation. This contrary to the findings of Usman (2015) which viewed the main implication of this finding is that, in education, teacher experience is being regarded by some as the key factor in making personnel policies that affect current employees. It is a cornerstone of traditional single-salary schedules, which also drives teacher transfer policies that prioritize seniority, and it is commonly considered a major source of inequity across schools, and therefore a target for redistribution. The underlying assumption here is that experience promotes effectiveness, and based on that, experience in teaching is a catalyst that ensures proper as well as effective curriculum implementation in schools.

The second findings of this study revealed that There was a significant impact of teachers' qualification on their effectiveness in implementing the Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. This findings agrees with that of Adefunke, Ayodele and Olufemi (2010) it was found that teachers' qualifications have positive impact on the successful effective implementation of curriculum at various levels of secondary schools. Teacher qualification is a reflection of competence, and the validity of any educational system is naturally dependent upon the quality of the teaching and the availability of competent teachers. Therefore, Hausa language teachers in particular need to be qualified enough to be able to guarantee successful implementation of the curriculum. These findings slightly differed with that of Abubakar (2014). In that study, it was discovered that teachers' quality (which may be termed as qualification) had no significant relationship with students' academic performance (which is a measure of curriculum implementation) and that only teachers' knowledge of subject matter played a significant role in the performance of students. This led to the general conclusion that teachers with deeper knowledge of subject matter (regardless of their qualification) produced better students than those with shallow knowledge of subject matter. This slight difference may be as a result of possible misconception by the respondents between teachers' quality and teachers' qualification. Otherwise, the teachers' knowledge of subject matter (which played a significant role in the performance of students) is definitely a product of teachers' qualification. Hence, the two finding may be interpreted to mean the same thing.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that teachers experience and qualification has positive significant impact on the use of methodology and the effectiveness in implementation of senior secondary school Hausa language Curriculum.

Recommendation

1. There is need for experienced teachers to monitor and mentor the inexperienced ones on the aspects of suitable teaching methods recommended for successful implementation of Hausa language curriculum among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, and the country at large
2. There is need for Zonal Education Quality Assurance staff to ensure proper monitoring and supervision of all schools offering Hausa language so as to have effective implementing of the Hausa language curriculum in Katsina State, and the same recommendation applies to all states ministries of education nationwide.

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References

- Aaronson, D., Barrow, L., & Sander, W. (2010) "Teachers and students achievement in the Chicago public high schools". *Journal of Labour Economics*, 25 (1), 95-135.
- Abdulmumin, S.A. (2008) Broadcasting in Hausa as a means of reaching nomadic Fulani of Nigeria. *JONAE Journal of Arts and Education*. IBB University Press, Lapai
- Abubakar, G. M. (2014). Perception of the relationship between teacher quality and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Kano metropolis. Published Master's thesis, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.
- Adadan, E., Irving, K.E., & Trundle, K.C (2009). Impacts of multi-representational instruction on high school students' conceptual understandings of the particulate nature of matter. *International Journal of Science Education*, 31(13), 1,743-1,775.
- Adenipekun, O. (2009). Rising figure of children, adult illiterates worry stakeholders. *The Vanguard*, January 22, 42.
- Brown, B.A., and Spang, E. (2011). Double talk: Synthesizing every day and science language in the classroom. *Science Education*, 92 (4), 708-732.
- Buhari, H. A. (2011). A comparative analysis of word-formation processes in English and Hausa. Unpublished Master's thesis, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.
- Busari, O.A (2008). *Politics in Africa*. Ibadan: Distance Learning Centre, University of Ibadan.
- Carl, A. (2009). *Teacher empowerment through curriculum development theory into practice*. Juta & Company Ltd.
- Carl, A. (2010). *Teacher empowerment through curriculum development: Theory into practice (2nd Ed.)* Albany: State University of New York Press.
- Carl, A. E (2009). *Teacher empowerment through curriculum development into practice*. Juta & Company Limited.
- Carless, D. (2009). Factors affecting classroom implementation: Task-based curriculum renewal in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Educational Reform* 8(4), 374-38.
- Shen, J., Gerard, L., and Bowyer, J. (2010). Getting from here to there: The roles of policy makers and principals in increasing science teacher quality. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 21(3), 283-307.
- Shi-Jer L, Hua-Lin T, Tien-Sheng T (2010). Using the Context, Input, Process and Product Model to Assess an Engineering Curriculum, *World Transactions on Engineering Technol. Educ.*
- Sinnema, C. (2009). *Monitoring and evaluating curriculum implementation. New Zealand final Evaluation Report on the Implementation of the New Zealand Curriculum, 2008 – 2009.*

- Shen, J., Gerard, L., and Bowyer, J. (2010). Getting from here to there: The roles of policy makers and principals in increasing science teacher quality. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 21(3), 283-307.
- Sinnema, C. (2009). Monitoring and evaluating curriculum implementation. New Zealand final Evaluation Report on the Implementation of the New Zealand Curriculum, 2008 – 2009.